

Developing Clinical Judgment Items from Task Model

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Developing Clinical Judgment Items

- Goals:
 - Provide examples of item/response types with suggested scoring
 - Provide example from initial development to final product
- Item Development
 - Item Writing Panels
 - Initial scenario & item development
 - Item Review Panels
 - Validate the content of the items
 - Producing Clinical Judgment Items
 - Turning raw materials from IWP into OP-ready items

Assessment Design Framework

Current Clinical Judgement Conceptual Model

Current Clinical Judgement Conceptual Model

Item/Response Types

With Scoring

New Item/Response Types

- Current use: MC, MR (scored 0/1), OL, and CR (fill in the blank)
- MR with partial credits
- **Drop-Down**
 - Cloze (within text)
 - Rationale
 - Within a table
- **Drag-and-Drop**
 - Bow-tie
 - Cloze
 - Fixed
 - Free
 - Multiple Response
 - Rationale
- **Highlighting**
 - Within text
 - Within a table
- **Matrix/Grid**
 - With multiple choice
 - With multiple response
- Scenario Scoring

Only 4 new actions a candidate would need to learn.

Only 1 new structure to learn with the Scenario items, e.g. multiple item case studies

Raw Scoring NGN Items

- Plus/Minus (+/-): Over/under responding is allowed
 - {correct, incorrect} = {+1, -1}
 - Total score = sum of response scores
 - If Total < 0, then Total = 0
- 0/1: When only specific # of responses allowed
 - 1 if selection is correct, otherwise 0
 - Total score = sum of response scores
- Rationale
 - When item has 2 conditions that must be met, e.g. do 'this' because of 'that'
 - 1 point for getting both responses correct, otherwise 0
- When multiple scoring elements present
 - Each element scored independently as above
 - Sum scores across elements

Drop-Down: Cloze

Element Score: 0/1
Item Score: Sum of element scores

NGN_W1_ITDC_Q2APR18 - Candidate Name I134049.1

Case Study
Screen 2 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 72-year-old male client admitted for a recent onset of abdominal pain.

Nurses' Notes

The client reports that he has not eaten in 4 days and has not been able to keep fluids down for the past 36 hours. He reports that his last bowel movement was 4 days ago, and it was dark in color. Upon assessment, the client's abdomen is distended, there are absent bowel sounds, and it is tender to the slightest touch. However, there is no rebound tenderness. Vital Signs: HR 115, BP 88/50, RR 16, T 100.0° F (37.8° C). Lab work is pending, and the client has no other significant medical history.

➤ Complete the following sentence by choosing from the list of options:

The most likely cause of the client's abdominal pain is due to the findings of and .

➔ End Exam ← Previous Next →

Drop-Down: Rationale

The nurse is preparing to administer scheduled medications to a 57-year-old male client for whom the nurse has the following data:

Diagnosis	total knee arthroplasty 24 hours ago
Current vital signs	blood pressure 142/90 pulse 48 respirations 20 oral temperature 99.3° F (37.4° C)
Allergies	ceftriaxone
Medical history	hyperlipidemia, hypertension, osteoarthritis, seasonal allergic rhinitis
Laboratory test results	complete blood count: hemoglobin 14.2 g/dL (142 g/L), platelets 420,000/mm ³ (420 x 10 ³ /L), white blood cell count 10,150/mm ³ (10.2 x 10 ³ /L) chemistry: serum sodium 151 mEq/L (151 mmol/L), serum potassium 4.2 mEq/L (4.2 mmol/L), blood urea nitrogen 18 mg/dL (6.4 mmol/L) coagulation: prothrombin time 12.3 seconds, activated partial thromboplastin time 27 seconds
Diet	low-sodium
Scheduled procedures	knee x-ray in 30 minutes

Scheduled medications to administer

atenolol 25 mg, p.o.
cefazolin 500 mg, I.V.
enoxaparin 30 mg, subcutaneously
hydrocodone/acetaminophen 5 mg/325 mg, 1 tablet, p.o.
pantoprazole 40 mg, p.o.
sertraline 50 mg, p.o.

Element Score: Rationale
Item Score: Sum of element scores

➤ Which three medications would require clarification prior to administration? Complete the following sentences by choosing from the lists of options.

The nurse should not administer the because .

The nurse should not administer the because .

The nurse should not administer the because .

Drop-Down: Table

Case Study
Screen 3 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old female who presents to the emergency department (ED) with worsening abdominal pain and has had a syncopal episode today. She has a surgical history of an appendectomy 6 months ago. She reports that she is sexually active, has irregular menses, and her last menstrual period was 18 days ago. No home medications.

Vital Signs: T 99°F (37.2°C), HR 128, RR 24, BP 100/65, SpO2 95% RA.

The patient has been diagnosed with ectopic pregnancy. Which of the following would be a priority to monitor the patient for?

➤ For each clinical finding, click to specify if it's high priority, medium priority, or low priority for the nurse.

Clinical findings	Priority
Hypotension:	Select...
Increasing pain:	Select...
Fever:	Select...
Ineffective coping mechanisms:	Select...

Score: 0/1

Drag-and-Drop: Bow-Tie

The home health nurse is planning care for an 86-year-old female client with heart failure and osteoporosis. The client has an unlicensed professional caregiver during the day on weekdays, and her 55-year-old son is her primary caregiver the rest of the time.

Complete the diagram below by dragging and dropping.

- Specify a complication for which the client is at increased risk.
- Specify two assessments the nurse can perform to monitor for the complication.
- Specify two interventions the nurse should perform as a way to reduce the risk of the complication.

Score: 0/1

Assessments to monitor for the complication	Potential complications	Preventive interventions
deep tendon reflexes	metabolic acidosis	provide range of motion exercises
mucous membranes	compression fractures	encourage adherence to anticonvulsant regimen
back pain	hyperkalemia	teach how to auscultate for a ventricular gallop
pupil reactivity	seizures	encourage weight-bearing exercise as tolerated
height		review client understanding of low-sodium diet
cranial nerve function		encourage adherence to bisphosphonate regimen
plantar flexion strength		teach to report sudden weight gain


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graph LR; A1[Assessment] --- PC[Potential complication]; A2[Assessment] --- PC; PC --- PI1[Preventive intervention]; PC --- PI2[Preventive intervention];
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Drag-and-Drop: Cloze

NGN_W1_ITDC_Q2APR18 - Candidate Name 1134057.1

Case Study
Screen 4 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses' Notes | **Prenatal Record**

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilatation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocotransducer. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

The client has a temperature of 102.1° F (38.9° C) at this time. The nurse notes that the fetal heart rate (FHR) is 170 with minimal variability and no accelerations present. Contractions are every 7 minutes, and last 50 seconds with moderate intensity. A category II fetal heart rate (FHR) tracing is noted.

➤ Drag words from the choices below to fill in each blank found in the following sentence:

The best outcomes for the client would be to _____
and _____. To achieve optimal outcomes, the nurse
should _____ and _____.

Word Choices

- Reduce maternal temperature
- Facilitate labor progression
- Improve fetal well-being
- Prepare for cesarean section
- Perform intrauterine resuscitation
- Administer intravenous antibiotics
- Discontinue intravenous oxytocin

➔ End Exam ← Previous Next →

Score: 0/1

Drag-and-Drop: Fixed

Case Study
Screen 3 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 45-year-old female client who had a right hip arthroscopy 3 days ago. The client had surgery due to a work related injury, which resulted in a labral tear of the hip. The client reports pain 10/10 on the numerical scale. The client was prescribed hydrocodone/acetaminophen 10/325 mg, p.o., every 4 hours, p.r.n., and has reported being out of her medication. Vital Signs: HR 75, BP 110/70, R 15, T 98.0° F (36.7° C). The client has a past medical history of breast cancer, which resulted in a double mastectomy, but has been in remission for 3 years.

The nurse is speaking with the client about pain control when the client states, "If I do not give my family member my narcotics, I will be forced to leave their home and live on the streets. My family member pays my bills because I am unable to work at this time."

➤ Drag the most and the least potential cause of the client's pain, to the box on the right.

Potential Causes
Giving or selling prescribed narcotics
Cultural implications such as stoicism
Undiagnosed complications after surgery
Misunderstanding of the pain scale
Attention seeking behavior

Cause by Likelihood	
Most likely	
Least likely	

Score: 0/1

Drag-and-Drop: Free

Element Score: +/-
Item Score: Sum of elements
If < 0, then = 0

Case Study Screen 6 of 6

The nurse has administered the client prescribed lorazepam for alcohol withdrawal symptoms.

- Drag the clinical findings on the left to the boxes on the right to indicate whether the medication was effective or ineffective. Choose only the findings that are appropriate.

Client findings	Effective	Ineffective
Tremors in the extremities		
Increased appetite		
Lower respiratory rate		
Agitation		
Dry skin		
Decreased pulse		

Each column is unique
scorable element

Drag-and-Drop: Multiple Response

Case Study Screen 3 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 72-year-old male client admitted for a recent onset of abdominal pain.

Nurses' Notes

The client reports that he has not eaten in 4 days and has not been able to keep fluids down for the past 36 hours. He reports that his last bowel movement was 4 days ago, and it was dark in color. Upon assessment, the client's abdomen is distended, there are absent bowel sounds, and it is tender to the slightest touch. However, there is no rebound tenderness. Vital Signs: HR 115, BP 88/50, RR 16, T 100.0° F (37.8° C). Lab work is pending, and the client has no other significant medical history.

The nurse is reporting the client's physical assessment findings to the physician. Drag to the box on the right the available diagnostic procedures that the nurse should recommend to the physician.

Diagnostic Procedures	
Available Diagnostic Procedures	Recommendation
Positron emission tomography (PET) scan	
Barium swallow study	
Abdominal computed tomography (CT) scan	
Abdominal ultrasound	
Small bowel x-ray with contrast	

Score: +/-

Drag-and-Drop: Free/Rationale

The nurse is planning care for a 72-year-old client who has heart failure and a stage III sacral pressure ulcer.

Complete the plan of care chart below by dragging and dropping to specify desired outcomes and evidence that each outcome has been met.

Potential Outcomes
Euolemia
Absence of hemorrhaging
Absence of wound infection
Regular bowel function pattern
Mucous membranes clean and moist
Baseline or increased activity tolerance

Plan of Care	
Desired Outcome	Evidence for Outcome

Evidence of Outcomes
Absence of hematuria
Pupils reactive to light
Absence of oral lesions
Reduction or absence of edema
Troponin levels within normal limits
Active bowel sounds in all four quadrants
White blood cell count within normal limits
Oxygen saturation consistently greater than 93%
Soft, formed bowel movement a minimum of twice in 4 days

Score:
Rationale

Highlight: In Text

NGN_W1_ITDC_Q2APR18 - Candidate Name

1134048.1

Case Study Screen 1 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 72-year-old male client admitted for a recent onset of abdominal pain.

Nurses' Notes

The client reports that he has not eaten in 4 days and has not been able to keep fluids down for the past 36 hours. He reports that his last bowel movement was 4 days ago, and it was dark in color. Upon assessment, the client's abdomen is distended, there are absent bowel sounds, and it is tender to the slightest touch. However, there is no rebound tenderness. Vital Signs: HR 115, BP 88/50, RR 16, T 100.0° F (37.8° C). Lab work is pending, and the client has no other significant medical history.

Click to highlight the assessment findings on the left that would require immediate follow-up.

Score: +/-

End Exam

Previous Next

Highlight: In Table

Case Study Screen 1 of 6

The emergency department (ED) nurse is assessing a client who has been experiencing left lower leg pain for the past 4 days. When trying to get out of the car today, the client had difficulty due to pain, which became more constant with cramping in the left calf.

	Admission Assessment Findings
Demographic Data	42-year-old female Hired driver; spends 12 hours per day sitting
Height and Weight	60 in (150 cm) 149.8 lb (68.1 kg)
Allergies	Cat dander
Cardiovascular	History of blood clots
Gastrointestinal	Dyspepsia
Musculoskeletal	Bilateral knee arthralgia
Reproductive	Menorrhagia Leiomyoma Family history of breast cancer
Psychosocial	Insomnia Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) Reports using marijuana on a regular basis for pain control
Vital Signs	T 98.4° (36.9° C), HR 102, RR 18, BP 116/76, O ₂ sat 100% on room air Pain rated 8/10 on the numerical scale

Click to highlight the findings on the left that would require immediate follow-up.

Score: +/-

Matrix/Grid: Multiple Choice

Score: 0/1

NGN_W1_ITDC_Q2APR18 - Candidate Name

1134051.1

Case Study Screen 4 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 72-year-old male client admitted for a recent onset of abdominal pain.

Nurses' Notes

The client reports that he has not eaten in 4 days and has not been able to keep fluids down for the past 36 hours. He reports that his last bowel movement was 4 days ago, and it was dark in color. Upon assessment, the client's abdomen is distended, there are absent bowel sounds, and it is tender to the slightest touch. However, there is no rebound tenderness. Vital Signs: HR 115, BP 88/50, RR 16, T 100.0° F (37.8° C). Lab work is pending, and the client has no other significant medical history.

➤ For each intervention, click to specify whether the intervention is indicated, neither indicated nor contraindicated, or contraindicated.

Nursing interventions	Indicated	Neither Indicated nor Contraindicated	
		Contraindicated	Contraindicated
Administer prescribed ondansetron intravenously	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Place the client in semi-Fowler's position	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Insert a nasogastric (NG) tube for continuous suction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Assess the client for signs of depression	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Administer prescribed ibuprofen p.o.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Each row is unique scorable element

End Exam

Previous Next

Matrix/Grid: Multiple Response

Case Study
Screen 3 of 6

Health History

Patient Record

A 78-year-old male presents to the emergency department (ED) complaining of severe abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, and bloating for the past 48 hours. The patient reports that he is a recovering alcoholic and has a history of cirrhosis of the liver. He reports a history of extensive abdominal surgery following an umbilical hernia repair and subsequent revisions of the surgical mesh. He is not sure if he still has his gallbladder or appendix. He had radiation treatments for prostate cancer 1 year ago. He reports that he has chronic constipation and uses a fiber supplement once or twice a week. He states his last bowel movement was 3 days ago. He has had some occasional watery diarrhea.

➤ For each clinical finding, click to specify whether it indicates peritonitis, bowel obstruction, or pancreatitis. The clinical findings may apply to one or more diagnoses.

Clinical finding	Peritonitis	Bowel Obstruction	Pancreatitis
Rebound pain	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Increased tenderness in the LLQ	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Scattered high pitched bowel sounds	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Dark, foul smelling emesis	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pain radiating to the back	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Each column is unique scorable element

Scenario/Case Study: Item Set

NGN_W1_ITDC_Q2APR18 - Candidate Name 1134024

Case Study Screen 1 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses' Notes

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocodynameter. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

Click to highlight the findings on the left that would require follow-up.

+/-

31 End Exam Previous Next

NGN_W1_ITDC_Q2APR18 - Candidate Name 1134024

Case Study Screen 2 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses' Notes **Prenatal Record**

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocodynameter. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

Complete the following sentences by choosing from the list of options.

The nurse should recognize that the fetal heart rate (FHR) may [Select...], the maternal temperature may [Select...], and the amniotic fluid may be [Select...] upon rupture of membranes if treatment is delayed.

Infection can cause adverse outcomes for the fetus, such as [Select...].

0/1

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NGN_W1_ITDC_Q2APR18 - Candidate Name 1134024

Case Study Screen 3 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses' Notes **Prenatal Record**

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocodynameter. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

Which of the following is most likely occurring based upon the information shown on the left? Select all that apply.

- Chorioamnionitis
- Slide effects of epidural placement
- Abruptio placenta
- Polyhydramnios
- Prolonged active phase of labor
- Anxiety attack
- Myxedema coma

+/-

31 End Exam Previous Next

NGN_W1_ITDC_Q2APR18 - Candidate Name 1134024

Case Study Screen 4 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses' Notes **Prenatal Record**

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocodynameter. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

The client has a temperature of 102.1° F (38.9° C) at this time. The nurse notes that the fetal heart rate (FHR) is 170 with minimal variability and no accelerations present. Contractions are every 7 minutes, and last 50 seconds with moderate intensity. A category II fetal heart rate (FHR) tracing is noted.

Drag words from the choices below to fill in each blank found in the following sentence:

The best outcomes for the client would be to _____ and _____ To achieve optimal outcomes, the nurse should _____ and _____

Word Choices

- Reduce maternal temperature
- Facilitate labor progression
- Improve fetal well-being
- Prepare for cesarean section
- Perform intrabreast resuscitation
- Administer intravenous antibiotics
- Discontinue intravenous oxytocin

0/1

31 End Exam Previous Next

NGN_W1_ITDC_Q2APR18 - Candidate Name 1134024

Case Study Screen 5 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses' Notes **Prenatal Record**

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocodynameter. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

Drag the potential steps the nurse should take to perform intrabreast resuscitation to the box on the right. Choose only the steps that are appropriate.

Potential Steps	Appropriate Steps
Place the client in left lateral position.	
Increase the infusion of titrated intravenous oxytocin.	
Administer 10 L of oxygen via nonrebreather mask.	
Report that the obstetrician artificially rupture the client's membranes.	
Check the client's center for changes in dilation.	
Increase the maintenance intravenous infusion.	

+/-

31 End Exam Previous Next

NGN_W1_ITDC_Q2APR18 - Candidate Name 1134024

Case Study Screen 6 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses' Notes **Prenatal Record**

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocodynameter. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

The nurse is assessing the client after performing intrabreast resuscitation.

For each finding, click to specify whether the finding indicated is effective, ineffective, or unrelated.

Assessment Finding	Effective	Ineffective	Unrelated
Maternal temperature of 100.4° F (38.0° C)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
FHR of 145	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Absent fetal variability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increase in bloody show	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Early decelerations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Maternal HR of 76	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

0/1

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From Raw Material to Finished Product

Sample Item Set Writing Template

Scenario	Cognitive Function (Layer 3)	Expected Behavior(s) Answer each expected behavior while referring to your scenario. Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Answer each factor while referring to your scenario. Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Items should have 5 or more response options. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.		
<p>A 28-year-old G4P2 at 40 weeks gestation is in active labor at 5 cm. She has an epidural and is comfortable. The patient has intact membranes. She is being augmented with oxytocin. The fetal heart rate tracing is normal. Her vital signs are: BP 115/78, P 88, R 15, T 100.4° F (38.0° C). The patient has had an uneventful pregnancy. She has had two previous spontaneous vaginal deliveries. She required a blood transfusion for a postpartum hemorrhage with her last delivery. She has a medical history of anxiety, hypothyroidism, and asthma.</p>	Recognize Cues	Recognize abnormal vs normal T 100.4° F (38.0° C)	Environment Cues: Implied labor and delivery unit	Which of the following are concerning <u>findings</u> : 1. Temp 100.4* 2. History of post-partum hemorrhage* 3. Oxytocin augmentation of labor 4. Intact membranes 5. History of anxiety		
		Recognize signs and symptoms T 100.4° F (38.0° C)	Patient Observation Cues: active labor at 5 cm; epidural; intact membranes; BP 115/78, P 88, R 15, T 100.4° F (38.0° C)	Rationale The low-grade fever could be evidence of developing chorioamnionitis. The history of post-partum hemorrhage places her at higher risk for a repeat hemorrhage.		
		Identify history of two previous spontaneous vaginal deliveries; blood transfusion for a postpartum hemorrhage with last delivery; medical history of anxiety, hypothyroidism, and asthma	Medical Record Cues: augmented with oxytocin; fetal heart rate tracing is normal; two previous spontaneous vaginal deliveries; blood transfusion for a postpartum hemorrhage with last delivery; medical history of anxiety, hypothyroidism, and asthma	Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.	
			Time Pressure Cues: 40 weeks gestation is in active labor	Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes		
		Connection between pathophysiology and client presentation: Fever could indicate infection. Maternal changes include increased pulse	Requires knowledge of: maternal complications signs/symptoms infection active labor oxytocin FHR tracings post-partum hemorrhage risks	What can you anticipate might happen next? 1. Maternal heart rate rises* 2. Fetal heart rate <u>rises</u> . * 3. Maternal temp continues to rise* 4. Foul smelling fluid upon rupture of membranes* 5. Decreased pain relief with epidural 6. Bright red vaginal bleeding. 7. Rapid progress of labor		
		Use findings/observations to determine client needs: T 100.4° F (38.0° C)		Rationale Maternal pulse is likely to rise with elevated maternal temp. Fetal heart rate will rise as a response to maternal pulse rising. Foul smelling fluid is a hallmark of infection. Maternal temps from infection will usually go much higher than 100.4. There is no stated reason why the epidural would stop providing pain relief. There is no stated reason why bright red bleeding would occur.		
				Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No	Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.	

Scenario	Cognitive Function (Layer 3) Item Type	Expected Behavior(s) Answer each expected behavior while referring to your scenario. Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Answer each factor while referring to your scenario. Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Items should have 5 or more response options. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.
<p>A 28-year-old G4P2 at 40 weeks gestation is in active labor at 5 cm. She has an epidural and is comfortable. The patient has intact membranes. She is being augmented with oxytocin. The fetal heart rate tracing is normal. Her vital signs are: BP 115/78, P 88, R 15, T 100.4° F (38.0° C). The patient has had an uneventful pregnancy. She has had two previous spontaneous vaginal deliveries. She required a blood transfusion for a postpartum hemorrhage with her last delivery. She has a medical history of anxiety, hypothyroidism, and asthma.</p>	<p>Prioritize Hypothesis</p>	<p>Prioritize (likelihood, risk, etc) infection contamination</p>	<p>Indicate Resources: FHR monitor Maternal monitor Epidural equipment</p>	<p>What two things could be happening? 1. Chorioamnionitis* 2. Low grade fever from epidural placement* 3. Normal labor 4. Placental abruption 5. Failure to progress in labor</p>
			<p>Indicate time pressure cues:</p>	<p>Rationale A temperature of 100.4 is part of the definition of chorioamnionitis but is not enough for stand-alone</p>
			<p>40 weeks gestation is in active labor</p>	<p>diagnoses. Women can have a reaction to prolonged epidural placement that causes a <u>low grade</u> fever with no further problems/complications. IT is not normal to have a temp 100.3F or higher during labor. Placental abruption doesn't cause a fever. There is no stated reason why her labor should fail to progress at this time.</p> <p>Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.</p>
	<p>Generate Solutions</p>	<p>Things to address: Maternal fever 5 cm dilation</p> <p>Things to avoid: systemic infection</p>	<p>Requires knowledge of: maternal complications signs/symptoms infection active labor oxytocin FHR tracings post-partum hemorrhage risks</p>	<p>Maternal temp is now 102.1F with rising maternal and fetal heart rates. What would be the goal of care at this time? 1. Reduce maternal fever* 2. Expedite delivery* 3. Reduce maternal anxiety 4. Prepare for post-partum hemorrhage 6. Prepare for cesarean delivery.</p> <p>Reducing maternal fever will decrease maternal pulse and decrease stress to the baby. Expediting delivery will help to decrease risk of transmission of infection to baby. Maternal anxiety is not a stated problem at this time. While there is an increased risk for post-partum hemorrhage that is not the most pressing issue. A cesarean delivery would increase the risk of systemic infection for the mother and should be avoided if possible.</p> <p>Rationale Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.</p>

Scenario	Cognitive Function (Layer 3) Item Type	Expected Behavior(s) Answer each expected behavior while referring to your scenario. Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each behavior.	Conditioning Factor(s) (Layer 4) Answer each factor while referring to your scenario. Adjust scenario/item stems to provide information for each factor.	Items Refer to the expected behaviors to help generate items. Items should have 5 or more response options. Mark the keys with an asterisk (*). Provide a rationale. Use resources as needed.
<p>A 28-year-old G4P2 at 40 weeks gestation is in active labor at 5 cm. She has an epidural and is comfortable. The patient has intact membranes. She is being augmented with oxytocin. The fetal heart rate tracing is normal. Her vital signs are: BP 115/78, P 88, R 15, T 100.4° F (38.0° C). The patient has had an uneventful pregnancy. She has had two previous spontaneous vaginal deliveries. She required a blood transfusion for a postpartum hemorrhage with her last delivery. She has a medical history of anxiety, hypothyroidism, and asthma.</p>	<p>Take Action</p>	<p>Request: antibiotics; CBC</p> <p>Administer: acetaminophen</p> <p>Perform (Skill):</p> <p>Document:</p> <p>Communicate</p>	<p>Requires knowledge of and experience with: maternal complications signs/symptoms infection active labor oxytocin FHR tracings post-partum hemorrhage risks</p>	<p>What are the most important interventions to take next?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Administer Acetaminophen as ordered* 2. Request orders for antibiotics* 3. Request orders for complete blood count* 4. Request order for artificial rupture of membranes 5. Prepare for cesarean delivery <p>Rationale Acetaminophen is an excellent fever reducer and not contraindicated in pregnancy. A regimen of antibiotics will help treat the infection and reduce the risk of transmission to the baby. A blood count will give a more complete picture of the infectious process. Rupturing membranes will increase the likelihood of transmission of the infection to the fetus.</p> <p>Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No</p> <p>Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.</p>
	<p>Evaluate Outcomes</p>	<p>Reassess: maternal temperature FHR maternal pulse</p>	<p>Requires knowledge of and experience with: maternal complications signs/symptoms infection active labor oxytocin</p>	<p>Which of these are evidence of positive outcomes related to nursing actions?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Maternal temp is now 100.2* 2. Fetal heartrate baseline is now 145.* 3. Maternal heartrate is 88.* 4. She is now 6 cm dilated. 5. Spontaneous rupture of membranes with foul smelling fluid.
			<p>FHR tracings post-partum hemorrhage risks</p>	<p>6. She has received 1 dose each of Ampicillin, Gentamycin and Clindamycin.</p> <p>Rationale Maternal temp has decreased after the acetaminophen administration. Fetal heartrate is WNL. Maternal heartrate is WNL. Labor progress is unrelated to these interventions. Rupture of membranes is unrelated to these interventions. The client receiving the antibiotics is an action not an outcome.</p> <p>Internal Use Only Meets CJ step: Yes or No</p> <p>Insert notes about accuracy, currency, fidelity, or entry-level here.</p>

Final Item Set

Using the Task Model Information

Case Study Screen 1 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses' Notes

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilatation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocotransducer. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

▶ Click to highlight the findings on the left that would require follow-up.

Case Study Screen 2 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses'
Notes

Prenatal
Record

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocotransducer. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

➤ Complete the following sentences by choosing from the list of options:

The nurse should recognize that the fetal heart rate (FHR) may , the maternal temperature may , and the amniotic fluid may be upon rupture of membranes if treatment is delayed.

Infection can cause adverse outcomes for the fetus, such as .

Case Study Screen 3 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses' Notes

Prenatal Record

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocotransducer. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

➤ Which of the following is most likely occurring based upon the information shown on the left? Select all that apply.

- Chorioamnionitis
- Side effects of epidural placement
- Abruptio placentae
- Polyhydramnios
- Prolonged active phase of labor
- Anxiety attack
- Myxedema coma

Case Study Screen 4 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses'
Notes

Prenatal
Record

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilatation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocotransducer. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

The client has a temperature of 102.1° F (38.9° C) at this time. The nurse notes that the fetal heart rate (FHR) is 170 with minimal variability and no accelerations present. Contractions are every 7 minutes, and last 50 seconds with moderate intensity. A category II fetal heart rate (FHR) tracing is noted.

➤ Drag words from the choices below to fill in each blank found in the following sentence:

The best outcomes for the client would be to _____
and _____. To achieve optimal outcomes, the nurse
should _____ and _____.

Word Choices

- Reduce maternal temperature
- Facilitate labor progression
- Improve fetal well-being
- Prepare for cesarean section
- Perform intrauterine resuscitation
- Administer intravenous antibiotics
- Discontinue intravenous oxytocin

Case Study Screen 5 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses' Notes

Prenatal Record

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocotransducer. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

- Drag the potential steps the nurse should take to perform intrauterine resuscitation to the box on the right. Choose only the steps that are appropriate.

Potential Steps

Place the client in left lateral position.

Increase the infusion of titrated intravenous oxytocin.

Administer 10 L of oxygen via nonrebreather mask.

Request that the obstetrician artificially rupture the client's membranes.

Check the client's cervix for changes in dilation.

Increase the maintenance intravenous infusion.

Appropriate Steps

Case Study Screen 6 of 6

The nurse is caring for a 28-year-old client who is gravida 4, para 2, is at 40 weeks gestation and is in active labor.

Nurses' Notes

Prenatal Record

The client is receiving titrated intravenous oxytocin for augmentation of labor via the secondary line on an intravenous pump. The client is also receiving maintenance intravenous fluid of lactated Ringer's solution at 125 mL/hr via an intravenous pump. The client has a cervical dilation of 5 cm and a cervical effacement of 100% with a fetal station of 0 in vertex presentation. Intact amniotic membranes noted. Category I tracing of fetal heart rate (FHR) of 150 bpm, with moderate variability, and 3 accelerations of 15 bpm over the baseline lasting 15 seconds via external ultrasound. The client is experiencing contractions every 5 minutes, which are lasting 70 seconds with moderate intensity via tocotransducer. Vital Signs: HR of 88, BP of 115/78, RR of 15, T of 100.4° F (38.0° C). Has a continuous epidural infusion of 0.25% bupivacaine with fentanyl running at 10 mL/hr. Pain 0/10 at this time. Client states, "I had postpartum hemorrhage with my last vaginal delivery and I required a blood transfusion." Medical history of hypothyroidism and asthma.

The nurse is assessing the client after performing intrauterine resuscitation.

➤ For each finding, click to specify whether the finding indicated is effective, ineffective, or unrelated.

Assessment Finding	Effective	Ineffective	Unrelated
Maternal temperature of 100.4° F (38.0° C)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
FHR of 145	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Absent fetal variability	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Increase in bloody show	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Early decelerations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Maternal HR of 76	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Cumulative Data Items: JUL17 to OCT18

Row Labels	RC	AC	PH	GS	TA	EO	KN	MULTI	Grand Total
CR	1	2	1	3		2			9
DD_Cloze	1	12	10	1	8	1	2		35
DD_Ration			2						2
DD_Table		3	3	2	2		1		11
DND_Bow								3	3
DND_Cloze	1								1
DND_Fixed		9	10	8	5	3	6	5	46
DND_Free		1	25	1	3	1			31
DND_MR	29	15	3	3	43	3			96
DND_Ration			1				2	2	5
HL_Table	6	6	1					1	14
HL_Text	27	7				18		3	55
Matrix_MC		7	2	32	12	12			65
Matrix_MR		11	2		1				14
MC	1	3	9	1	3	5	16	1	39
MR	39	38	17	30	24	23		3	174
MULTI								35	35
OR			1		8				9
Grand Total	105	114	87	81	109	68	27	53	644

Thank you